

Synthetic controls in nanoparticles for focusing and enhancing neurodegenerative signals

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The need for precise diagnostic tools in neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's is crucial for early detection and monitoring. This work presents the synthesis and structural characterization of biphasic magnetite/gold (Fe₃O₄/Au) nanoparticles (MNPs) aimed at enhancing the detection of neurodegenerative signals. We explored several synthetic approaches using the aqueous coprecipitation method, including core-shell systems, dumbbell-like structures, and magnetite matrices embedded with Au nanoparticles, achieving high reproducibility in particle size, morphology, and magnetic properties. The core-shell systems consist of a magnetite (Fe₃O₄) core encased in a gold (Au) shell, while the dumbbell-like structures feature magnetite particles connected by gold segments. Characterization techniques such as Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and Vibrating Sample Magnetometry (VSM) confirmed precise control over magnetic properties and particle size. This control enabled the development of an optimized nanoparticle system for bioassays in Alzheimer's diagnostics. The core-shell design provides dual functionality: magnetic manipulation for enhanced sensitivity and purification, and gold for electrochemical signal amplification, improving diagnostic precision for neurodegenerative diseases.

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4 key words

Biphasic magnetite/gold nanoparticles

Alzheimer's Disease diagnostics